

A Workshop on the Interpretation/Use Argument and Concept Inventories: A Step towards Validated Test Instruments

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Abstract. Many researchers and educators want to use reliable, valid and fair test instruments for assessing e. g., students' competences. However, recent literature reviews identified a lack of validated instruments in K-12. Furthermore, earlier validity frameworks suffer from a lack of priority between multiple sources of validity. This led to different usages of validity arguments in computing education. Kane's framework and the APA standards provide a guideline for researchers presenting evidence to evaluate their inferences. This workshop aims to offer a practical introduction to Kane's framework by analysing the evidence present by eleven validated computer science concept inventories (CIs). Based on the evaluation of the evidence using the interpretation/use argument the four inferences of Kane's framework will be the content of this workshop. The result will be a table with evidence of the eleven CIs according to the IUA that researchers can use as a guide for their own validation studies.

Keywords: Computer Science Education · Validation · Interpretation/Use Argument (IUA) · Concept Inventory

1 Introduction

One essential part of computer science education (CSE) is assessing students' competences [14]. Competences are often measured by assessing students' content knowledge (CK) as one facet of their competences [16]. Several options exist for assessing students' CK according to Román-González et al. [12] such as diagnostic tests that can serve as pre- and post-tests, formative tests, and literacy tests (skill transfer tests). The latter measure students' problem-solving skills in real-world contexts (e. g., the *Bebras tasks* [5]). Formative (process-accompanying) tests can provide students with direct feedback (e. g., *Dr. Scratch* [9]). Diagnostic tests such as the *Computational Thinking test (CTt)* [13] can be administered in pre-test conditions (with students without prior CS experience) and post-test conditions to measure e. g. an effect of an intervention. Román-González et al. [12] concluded in their comparison of different tests that skill transfer tests are not adequate as a pre-test but should be used for follow-up tests. Therefore, diagnostic tests and their validation will be the focus of this workshop.

Options for diagnostic tests include exams, quizzes, or modified versions of tests they know (e.g. Bebras tasks). However, Tew & Dorn [15] outline several challenges when using those (unvalidated) diagnostic tests such as that (1) the test does not assess the intended skills or CK (criterion validity [10]), (2) test items (tasks) have a bias towards a subgroup (e.g., an item is more difficult for female students than male [6]) and (3) the test does not cover the curricula and only that what was intensively taught in class (content validity [3]). Hence, researchers and teachers alike should focus on validated tests to assess e.g., the effect of an intervention according to several experts [15, 6, 10].

Systematic literature reviews are a good starting point when searching for validated tests. Despite numerous reviews emphasizing the recent expansion of validated assessments in the field [8, 14, 1], a significant number of CSE researchers continue to face challenges in identifying valid tests for assessing students' CK within K-12 settings. Currently, there is only one validated CS concept inventory (CI) available for the K-12 educational context according to Ali et al. [1]: the *Middle Grade Computer Science Concept Inventory (MG-CSCI)*[11]. Ten validated CIs exist for higher education [1].

A CI is a standardized multiple choice CK test that assess core CS concepts (e.g. variables) and has empirically validated students' misconceptions about these concepts as distractors [1, 14]. Thereby, educators can use students' answers to identify knowledge gaps or misconceptions as well as measure the effect of an intervention [1]. The CI has several development steps to verify that the items prompt the intended cognitive process and are not subject to guessing [1]. These steps include (1) a literature review and expert validation of core CS concepts, (2) identify misconceptions, (3) item development, (4) piloting the items with a group of students, revision and (5) validating the CI [1]. The focus of the workshop is on six validated CIs as they underwent qualitative as well as quantitative analysis and were not tested only once with a group of students. The CS topics of the CIs include concepts of variables, loops, conditionals, and algorithms [11], digital logic concepts (e.g., state transitions), recursion, cybersecurity, and data structures (e.g., binary tree) [1].

1.1 The Interpretation/Use Argument (IUA)

Kane's review of validation research [7] and Cook et al. [4] analysis for medical education provide an overview of the 100 year long evolution of validity research. Starting with content validity (to which extend the test covers the concept) and criterion validity (if the tests scores correlate with another measure of the concept, e.g. self-efficacy or other validated test scores) to several sources of evidence (content, responses, internal structure and more). The latter approach led researchers to emphasize on varying evidence of validity [7, 4]. The newest framework from Kane [7] tackles this issue by focusing on inferences drawn in planing and evaluating the proposed validity argument called *Interpretation/Use Argument (IUA)*. The approach is to first propose the claims (how to *interpret* the results and how to *use* the assessment) and then to evaluate the evidence supporting them. Each piece of evidence should be presented to strengthen the

argument. It is key to identify the weakest links and reevaluate the inferences drawn by the authors to create a cohesive argument [7]. Closely aligned with the APA standards [2] Kane’s framework [7] consists of four stages and can be applied to both qualitative and quantitative assessment instruments to structure the pieces of evidence. These stages include: *scoring* (e.g., a CI with its scoring rubric), *generalisation* (e.g., sampling strategy and other factors that led to the test score in the test setting), *extrapolation* (e.g., authenticity of test setting and implications on a real life performance), and *implications* (e.g., planned actions based on the test results) [7]. The implications of test results are especially important [7]. They can influence whether a student passes or fails, the reproducibility of studies, and whether findings—for instance, comparisons between plugged vs. unplugged sessions—are valid.

2 Information on the workshop

This workshop is of significance for the ISSEP community as some CSE researchers still validate tests without conforming to IUA and APA standards or provide insufficient evidence, often using not validated assessments, age-inappropriate tools, or unsuitable formats for pre- and post-tests [12]. Thereby, the **goal of the workshop** is to introduce participants to CIs [1], the IUA [7] and APA standards [2]. This will be achieved by an introduction of the background (CI, IUA, APA standards; 20 min), a discussion on the participants experience with validation (20 min) and a working phase where the participants analyse existing CSE CI validation studies according to the literature review of Ali et al. [1] to find pieces of evidence for the four stage of the IUA (40 min). The product at the end of the workshop will be a table analogue to Cook et al. [4] where pieces of evidence are documented (10 min). This product will be shared and can serve as a guideline for future validation studies in CSE.

Target audience: the workshop is intended for CSE researchers without any experience (e.g., Ph.D. students that might be interested in test development or evaluating their intervention) to participants that already published validation studies and are interested how their colleagues have structured their evidence.

Workshop leader: Tobias Bahr is an Acting Professor of Didactics of Computer Science at the University of Potsdam. He completed his Ph.D. *summa cum laude* at the University of Stuttgart in 2024. His research interests include assessment methodologies, gender studies, and CT in K-12 education. His expertise consists of the development, adaptation, and validation of CS assessment instruments published in several venues including the ITiCSE conference.

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